

Development strategies for multi-robot teams in context of planetary exploration

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Abstract—In the realm of extraterrestrial exploration, robotics has primarily centered around the deployment of large and complex rovers for planetary missions. Therefore, the risk of total loss in the event of an error is relatively high for a single complex system. Currently, the issue is being addressed by relying on redundancy, which makes the systems even more complex. In contrast, there are approaches to have several robotic systems acting together in a multi-robotic team to fulfill different tasks, which can still be carried out with the remaining systems, if one system fails. The German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence has developed various approaches with different heterogeneous teams and successfully tested them in a number of field tests. This paper provides an overview of the already conducted work and provides an insight into future strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the space era, human beings desired to go to the moon or distant planets to explore them and also to build infrastructures. This requires not only long-term planning, but also brings logistical challenges. Health risks to humans from radiation and other external influences must also be taken into account. On the way there, solutions from the robotic field were found for the first time. Exploration of foreign planets by robotic systems is also currently taking place [1], [2]. Further development is now moving towards multi-robotic teams that are able to develop an infrastructure or provide support for humans to help with planetary exploration. The idea behind the integration of several robotic systems acting together as a team, is to reduce the probability of a mission failing. Each system can fulfill certain tasks on its own, which together as a team can master greater challenges during an exploration mission. If one system fails, the other systems can continue to work. If modules are included, it is also possible to add features to the systems involved or to replace integrated defective modules so that the systems can have a lower failure rate. Other approaches include using modules to build a system on site that is intended to fulfill certain mission requirements. The main advantage of multi-robotic teams is not only to keep the payload low during transportation, but also to reduce the amount of stowage space required, as compared to a large complex rover such as the Perseverance rover [2].

The research in the area of multi-robot cooperation covers a wide range from terrestrial applications to preparing a basis for orbital and planetary applications [3]. There are approaches to multi-robotic cooperation, in which several sys-

tems act together [4], [5], as well as multi-robotic teams, in which not only mobile systems cooperate with each other but also expand the entire mission scenario by (re-)configuring the systems involved [6]. Also there are approaches of using human-robot interaction within a multi-robot team [7] or human-machine collaboration as a team with one robotic system interacting with one human (astronaut) [8].

Experiences to date show that artificial intelligence is indispensable for successful missions with multi-robotic teams. This applies to autonomous decisions by the systems involved in the event of possible communication delays as well as autonomous decisions within the team. This ranges from autonomous mapping and navigation to communication, including decisions in the team on how to (re)configure in order to fulfill the mission tasks accordingly [9].

This paper describes the research within the German Center for Artificial Intelligence - Robotics Innovation Center (DFKI RIC) in the area of multi-robotic teams for planetary exploration, from the (re-)configurability point of view of the systems involved depending on mission requirements to cooperation between robot systems. The outcomes of completed projects are presented, as well as their further use and development in current projects. Finally, the future roadmap as well as realization and feasibility will be discussed in the outlook.

II. EXISTING MULTI-ROBOTIC TEAMS

DFKI RIC has set itself the goal of not only developing and applying artificial intelligence to robotic systems for space applications, but also developing systems that can perform realistic actions in an approximately simulated lunar or Martian environment. The evolution of the development of multi-robotic teams at DFKI RIC ranges from teams with different robotic systems acting together to teams whose systems can be coupled together to build a corresponding cooperative team. Important features are autonomy in navigation and mapping of individual systems as well as cooperative mapping, in which the systems merge their recorded data to create a common map. Other important features are communication between the individual systems as well as communication over long ranges with so-called ground control centers. (Re-)configurability enables, for example, the expansion of individual systems with modular components as well as combinability between robotic systems. This is where autonomy comes into play to enable the robotic teams to decide for themselves which configurability should be carried out and how. The coupling of the systems with each other as well as the extension of the systems with

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modular components takes place with the help of a so-called multifunctional interface [10]. Robot framework, using ROS and ROCK¹, enables a basis for low level control of the multi-robot teams.

The following subsections describe the research at DFKI RIC within different multi-robotic teams and their outcomes.

A. RIMRES (Reconfigurable Integrated Multi-Robot Exploration System)

The main goal of project RIMRES was to develop a modular, reconfigurable, heterogeneous multi-robot system to simulate lunar crater exploration missions with a terrestrial demonstrator. An important criterion in the project was to develop the ability to reconfigure in order to obtain both an approach to (re)use resources and to increase the overall efficiency of the system while maintaining redundancy.

Fig. 1. Sherpa using its manipulator to lift CREX. A possible use-case is the deployment of CREX off a landing unit. Furthermore, a reconfiguration-scenario where CREX is used as a six-fingered hand is also conceivable. (source: DFKI GmbH)

Using the mission scenario as a basis, a leg-wheeled rover Sherpa (Sherpa: Expandable Rover for Planetary Applications) was developed that enables energy-efficient transport of a six-legged robot CREX (CRater EXplorer) specialized in moving around in crater regions, see Figure 1. An electro-mechanical interface (EMI) [10] enabled the modular design of the multi-robot system, including immobile payload objects and a robotic arm that allows the manipulation of payload objects and the utilization of modularity through reconfiguration. To allow for reconfiguration each of these systems is at least equipped with one EMI. A low-level controller is used to manage the heterogeneous and modular robot hardware system. The design between the robots and within the robot is taken into account. The software architecture uses a model-based approach and achieves a balance between specialization and generalization so that the same software base is used on each (sub-)system of the robot team. Furthermore, a distributed and dynamic team structure is supported. In the project, it was possible to use the control system to check the most important reconfiguration capabilities such as stacking and docking. Stacking describes

the ability to couple a payload consisting of several payload elements with the help of the rovers manipulator via the EMI. This also includes docking CREX to Sherpa via the EMI by a semi-autonomous approach. Other goals achieved in the project were to demonstrate teleoperation and semi-autonomous operation and to prove the suitability of the control approach for the multi-robot system [6] [11].

B. TransTerra (Semi-autonomous cooperative exploration of planetary surfaces including the installation of a logistic chain as well as consideration of the terrestrial applicability of individual aspects)

Building on the experiences and outcomes of Project RIMRES, the further development of a multi-robotic team was driven forward in TransTerra. The developed EMI, the payload modules, the Sherpa rover and the control approaches, teleoperation and semi-autonomous operations used served as the basis from RIMRES for further development in TransTerra. The main focus was on establishing a logistics chain with heterogeneous robotic systems that are capable to be (re-) configured according to mission requirements for a planetary surface exploration [12]. The involved robotic team consists of various systems like the mobile rovers SherpaTT and Coyote3 [13] as well as immobile elements like a BaseCamp (stationary module) and portable modular payload-items (PLIs) [14]. The key element the further developed modular EMI which ensure different combinations between the involved systems, as far as a system is equipped with at least one EMI.

Fig. 2. SherpaTT and Coyote3 during their cooperative sample return mission (source: DFKI GmbH)

The developed mobile and immobile systems were tested in a field test to simulate the mission a Mars-like environment. In addition to testing for a Mars sample return mission as a team, the functions and features of the two mobile systems SherpaTT and Coyote3 were also validated (Fig. 2) [15].

In preparation for a sample return mission, both rovers underwent thorough testing to verify their sensor calibration and autonomous behavior. The outcome of the field tests

¹<https://github.com/dfki-ric>

was that both systems were able to autonomously navigate to the target independently while simultaneously mapping their environment using a graph-based SLAM approach. Furthermore, a distributed mapping concept, which should enable cooperative tasks and rendezvous maneuvers, was successfully tested. This involved merging maps created independently by both systems into a consistent global map (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Multi Level Surface (MSL) Map. Color indicates height, color cycle repeats each 1 m in height (source: DFKI GmbH) [15]

Targeted tasks such as taking soil samples were also carried out as a successful mission sequence. SherpaTT used the manipulator arm to autonomously dock the payload item, which contained the sampling module, with the end effector, consisting of the EMI, using visual odometry. SherpaTT and Coyote3 were also successfully tested in a closed mission sequence controlled from a ground station in Bremen, Germany. The control station was equipped with a multi-projection screen and, together with a two-armed upper body exoskeleton, complex multi-robot mission sequences were carried out in Utah from Bremen².

C. PRO-ACT (Planetary Robots Deployed for Assembly and Construction Tasks)

The PRO-ACT (Planetary Robots deployed for Assembly and Construction Tasks) project aimed to develop and demonstrate key technologies for robot collaboration in the construction of future ISRU (In-Situ Resource Utilization) facilities on the Moon. The target was to have heterogeneous autonomous robots (Veles - a rover with six wheels and a 7-DoF (Degree of Freedom) arm [16], Mantis - a six-legged walking system, and a mobile gantry that can be used for payload manipulation or 3D printing) cooperate with each other in order to jointly explore an unknown area, cooperatively unload and transport large components, and assemble an ISRU facility on the Moon [17]. Outcomes from previous operational grants (OGs) of PERASPERA had to be taken into account as a base line. These included developed framework software and robot guidance software. Most important for the project were the topics

- multi-robot system architecture,

²<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pvKIzldni68>

- task assignment through mutual negotiation,
- cooperative task execution,
- single and multi-agent perception, mapping, and localization,
- cooperative manipulation planning and control,
- robot hardware adaptation.

which were accommodated in mission cooperative scenarios like mission planning, manipulation, transportation and mapping. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, these scenarios had to be split for the final demonstration, due to hygienic restrictions not allowing all robotic systems to be operated together in the same place. Once during the project period, the Mantis and Veles systems were able to come together in the outdoor area of the DFKI RIC for initial implementations and initial performance tests. This was only possible under strict conditions and with limited human presence. In the further course of the project the systems had to remain at their respective locations.

Fig. 4. Mantis and Veles conducting a cooperative mapping sequence in an outdoor area (source: DFKI GmbH)

Although there was the Covid-19 pandemic restriction, the project was able to successfully demonstrate cooperative mapping, grading, end effector tool exchange and gantry deployment³ (Fig. 5).

The virtual and physical remote cooperative manipulation scenarios posed a great challenge as the problems had to be understood remotely and solved with a minimum of information. The virtual manipulation demo was conducted with certain simplified steps as time and feasibility were limited due to the remote nature of the demo.

To be able to control the robotic systems remotely, the project consortium designed a remote approach for the integrations and the final demonstrations. The implementation was successful and showed that it is possible to access the robot from far distances (Belgium, Poland, Spain, France to Germany) via an internet connection. It also showed that a stable connection is essential for this remote approach, but it opens a new door for future integration projects where a fusion of both approaches (physical and remote) clearly benefits the integration and testing of different software components, especially when a project is developed by different partners in different countries.

³<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=spSIQOeMKWc>

Fig. 5. Veles (left) and Mantis (right) during the cooperative mapping sequence. Below the robots are the mapped areas [17]

The test results have shown that remote monitoring and control of multi-robot systems is possible without the physical presence of humans, which is essential for planetary applications. However, they also show that higher levels of autonomy need to be developed so that the robots can independently decide how to perform a task in the event of delays or failure of communication links to the control center (e.g. on Earth). The experimental results have also shown that it makes sense to equip the multi-robot systems involved with higher and configurable levels of autonomy and goals so that the robots can independently decide how to fulfill their assigned goals and react to unexpected events without the presence of humans [18] [19] [17].

D. CoRob-X (Cooperative Robots for Extreme Environments)

In the recently concluded research project CoRob-X [20], funded by the European Union, three prototypes for next generation exploration rovers were used to explore and map the surface area around a skylight as well as the skylight itself and the attached lava tube underneath. The entire mission was subdivided in four mission phases, which were successfully demonstrated during a field test campaign⁴ on Lanzarote, Canary Islands. The robotic team consisted of the hybrid wheeled-legged rover SherpaTT [13], with its strong manipulator, the lightweight and cost-effective Luvmi-X⁵ rover, and the small four-wheeled skid-steering rover Coyote3 [21], equipped with a ground-penetrating radar [26] to locate the sub-terrestrial lava tube and collect scientific data.

In the first mission phase the area around the skylight was cooperatively explored and mapped by SherpaTT and LUVMI-X, while Coyote3 recorded a radagramm to identify the location of the lava tube. The exploration was conducted autonomously. Only corner coordinates of the surface area to be explored were sent to the systems. In the second mission phase Luvmi-X deployed a sensor cube into the skylight to construct a 3D-model that was used to define the most suitable entry point for mission phase three. In this complex

phase SherpaTT automatically deployed a specifically developed tether management and deployment system (TMDS) to the ground nearby the skylight. Afterwards Coyote3 drove onto the TMDS and docked to it, while SherpaTT's manipulator remained connected to the TMDS via a tether cable. After successful docking, Coyote3 started driving towards the skylight and commanded the winch inside the TMDS to unspool the tether cable. This allowed Coyote3 to rappel down the vertical skylight walls and into the lava tube, while being supported by SherpaTT through the tether. In order to avoid damage on the manipulator, SherpaTT autonomously moved its base and arm to minimize the load. Once Coyote3 arrived on the bottom of the lava tube it undocked from the TMDS and went on exploring the lava tube in the fourth mission phase.

While the robotic systems and software modules use a variety of underlying frameworks, a lightweight and framework independent library is used to serve as common communication interface [19].

Fig. 6. SherpaTT, Coyote3 and Luvmi-X in front of a skylight during the field test on Lanzarote, Canary Islands (source: DFKI GmbH).

III. CURRENT RESEARCH

In the next subsections, current research work in the context of multi-robot cooperation will be presented.

A. VaMEx3 (Valles Marineris Explorer)

VaMEx3 is the third phase of an interdisciplinary research program initiated and funded by the German Space Agency at DLR. The main objective of this research initiative is the exploration of the Valles Marineris on the Martian surface. The third phase is focused on developing and integrating a robotic team to demonstrate cooperative and autonomous exploration in an analogue field test scenario [22]. The robotic team is heterogeneous and consists of a drone, several rovers and a crawler. By design each swarm member has different capabilities. This heterogeneity is further reinforced by equipping each robotic agent with a different sensor suite ranging from common stereo-cameras and lidars to project internal developments like a sun sensor, radio beacons and

⁴<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YNkbi8ta3yw>

⁵<https://www.h2020-luvmi-x.eu/about/>

radar systems. The integrity of all sensor data is continuously evaluated before they are fused through a multi-robot-multi-sensor SLAM in order to reach a robust and fail-safe navigation and absolute localisation.

The defined mission scenario, depicted in 7, assumes a successful entry, descent and landing operation. The lander serves as a central communication and computation hub.

Fig. 7. Mission overview for the demonstration scenario in VaMEX3.

While the rovers set up a local network with radio beacons, orbiter images are used to manually identify the lander and these radio beacons to determine the absolute geo-position. This is the only manual intervention during the entire mission. To start exploration a scouting drone uses the local network and its on-board sensors to explore a region of interest. The collected sensor data is geo-tagged through Terrain Relative Navigation and a multi-sensor SLAM. After return of the drone to the lander, the collected data is used to generate a high resolution 3D-map. This map can then be used by a global planner to plan a safe route for the unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs). For further exploration, tasks are auctioned and automatically distributed for the regions of interest. The rovers use the global map to navigate to the designated site. In the region of interest another local navigation network is established by deploying radio beacons. Thus enabling precise collaborative navigation with centimeter accuracy. Points of interest are explored within the region of interest. For challenging terrain, the crawler can be deployed. Furthermore, the UAVs can be summoned for support in mapping activities or to serve as communication relays, facilitating data transfer from the target area to the lander.

B. Human-integrated Swarm Exploration (HiSE)

For humans to colonize Mars, the Martian terrain needs to be thoroughly explored to enable ISRU needed to establish production and human conducive habitats. A step towards this goal, in collaboration with partners from the University of Bremen, HiSE [23] is a novel approach towards designing

an integrative framework used for collaborative extraterrestrial exploration by hybrid (human-robot) teams. The rovers are tasked with optimum exploration of Martian terrain for resources *i.e.* regions of scientific interest. Exploration and related tasks in a highly uncertain and dynamic environment like Mars pose several challenges to rovers and astronauts. When resources are scarce and there is limited knowledge about their distribution, missions could be more time and energy consuming. Relevant information from the rovers is transmitted to the astronaut crew for verification and resource sampling, requiring minimal communication latency on unreliable channels. The data gathered by the rovers is also often bulky and difficult to interpret by the human, given that their decisions must be quick and precise. HiSE aims to tackle the aforementioned challenges by integrating a robust multi-rover exploration strategy with semantic communication and extended reality (XR)-based visualization techniques. There is special emphasis on situation awareness [24] through mutually aware exploration and communication. The framework architecture has four layers, namely, operation, information storage and sharing, visualization and sampling, and mission planning and exploration. The project will conclude with human-in-the-loop trials (human test subjects and simulated robots) and a proof-of-concept demonstration (physical robots) of the same. This will consist of human test subjects who act as astronauts communicating with robots via semantic communication channels. The robots perform the exploration tasks and send relevant information – such as locations of RoIs (Regions of Interest) – that is visualized by the humans using XR technology. The framework will serve as a test-bed for future human-robot mission strategies.

IV. OUTLOOK

Both orbital and planetary missions are a challenging task. Mission success requires a highly flexible and adaptable system for unexpected situations. An innovative paradigm shift towards this goal represents a logical progression in enhancing the capabilities of extraterrestrial missions. We consider modular and reconfigurable interoperable heterogeneous robotic systems with the ability to reuse and rebuild complex and individual structures based on modules. Teams of heterogeneous robotic agents composed of such complex systems, including humans, are required both for planetary missions, such as exploration of the Moon and Mars and habitat creation, as well as for the orbital construction of large structures such as solar farms or space stations.

We are currently developing modular components that can be used to expand existing robotic teams. In contrast to previous projects/developments, these are parts that are independent of existing systems and COTs. This means that the modular systems are to be designed in such a way that they can be integrated into existing systems with the help of a multifunctional interface. The basis comes from the RIMRES and TransTerra projects. This development takes place in MODKOM (Modular components as Building Blocks for application-specific configurable space robots), which also has the special feature of developing an extra toolbox from

which systems can be assembled from software and hardware modules according to mission requirements [25].

In view of this, the future trajectory of our research involves the development of complex and adaptive systems, envisioned as automatically reconfigurable robotic structures, characterized by subsystems based on specific interfaces and modules. To manage the increasing task complexity we want to advance robotic frameworks that can be applied on individual systems and form a standardization to build upon. Key aspects in handling complex tasks with larger teams of robotic systems involving dynamic physical mythologies will be software for sharing knowledge by the individual with the team as well as the exchange of information about their own capabilities and learning models of the capabilities of others. Subsequently negotiation algorithms for autonomous distribution of sub-tasks are required in order to reach the overall goal addressed to the team in an efficient and optimal manner using the full potential of the heterogeneous team. Future research in the area of knowledge representation will be conducted to support the inclusion of humans into the team. This will result in mutual information gain which will boost the team's overall performance. Technologies that will help to realize those required software components will rely on Machine Learning techniques. These solutions will exploit the synthesis of human cognitive intelligence and robotic autonomy to overcome the challenges that may arise in dynamic extraterrestrial missions.

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